

NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING BY RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

The Raman effect is a phenomenon observed in the scattering of light as it passes through a material, such that it undergoes a change in frequency and a random alteration in phase. The intensity of Raman scattering is very low in comparison to that of Rayleigh and Tyndall scattering, which both have the same frequency and a definite phase relationship to the incident light. Raman scattering is approximately uniform in all directions and can be analysed spectroscopically. Interest in the Raman effect was revived by the laser which provided a highly collimated, small-diameter beam of intense, coherent, polarised and monochromatic radiation. Laser Raman spectroscopy has been widely used to study different aspects of reinforcement fibres and their composites. This paper will review the application of the technique.

INTRODUCTION

The development of fibre reinforced composite materials has been accompanied by rapid advances in the understanding of the physics and chemistry of materials. This new knowledge has been combined with the developments in electronics and computing to produce the new discipline of non-destructive testing (NDT). Sharpe [1] has comprehensively documented new research techniques in NDT and the Royal Society recently held a two-day discussion meeting on novel techniques [2]. The use of non-destructive testing techniques for fibre-reinforced plastic composites has been comprehensively reviewed, [3].

The major techniques of NDT for composite materials are radiography, ultrasonics and acoustic emission, but thermal, optical, electrical, magnetic, vibration and chemical spectroscopic properties have all been exploited. This review will concentrate on one specific spectroscopic approach - Raman Spectroscopy.

In 1928 Raman [4] reported the discovery of frequency-shifted lines in the scattered light spectra of transparent substances. Most light scattering occurs without gain or loss of energy, and in Rayleigh and Tyndall scattering the emergent light retains the frequency of the incident light and bears a definite phase relationship. Raman scattering differs as the light undergoes a constant frequency shift and has a random alteration in phase. Raman shifts can be positive or negative: Stokes lines are shifted to longer wavelengths (energy loss) while anti-Stokes lines are shifted to shorter wavelengths (energy gain). The intensity of Raman scattering is roughly 1/1000 th of the Rayleigh scattering in liquids and even less in gases. The phenomenon is usually referred to as "combination scattering" in the Soviet literature, [5 - 7].

Raman scattering occurs during vibrational motions of segments of molecules which produce a polarisation or distortion of the electron charge of the chemical bonds. The stretching motion of a homonuclear diatomic molecule causes Raman scattering. Raman effect provides more information about the nonpolar portions of organic molecules than infra-red spectroscopy, which is a complementary technique.

The advances in instrumentation since 1928, and particularly the development of the laser, have changed a little used technique into a prominent branch of molecular spectroscopy. Lasers produce intense, polarised, coherent and highly-collimated small-diameter beams of monochromatic radiation which are ideal for Raman spectroscopy. Selection of lasers is determined by the particular application, with argon-ion or krypton-ion 1-10W sources used in continuous-wave (CW) operation or semi-conductor and excimer lasers used for pulsed sources. Tunable dye lasers can provide a continuous selection of excitation wavelengths between the ultraviolet and near infra-red and are commonly used in the excitation of resonance Raman scattering (RRS). Raman scattering is analysed by spectroscopic means. The scattering is approximately uniform in all directions and is usually studied at right angles to the incident beam, to prevent interaction between the excitation beam and the detector.

When the incident beam has a frequency range within the absorption band of the molecule, the radiation may be scattered by two processes:

- resonance fluorescence, or
- resonance Raman effect.

Resonance fluorescence differs from resonance Raman in that the absolute frequencies of the fluorescent spectrum do not shift when the exciting beam

frequency is changed, provided that the latter remains within the absorption band. The absolute frequencies of the resonance Raman effect shift by exactly the amount of shift in the exciting beam frequency, as in the normal Raman effect. The intensity of the resonant form may be two or three orders of magnitude greater than that for normal Raman effect. Behringer has presented excellent review articles on resonance Raman spectroscopy (RRS), [8, 9].

The non-destructive examination and chemical analysis of microscopic samples can be achieved by the use of microscope optics to focus the laser light onto the sample and to collect the scattered light. The technique was developed at NBS Washington and first reported in 1974 [10]. Typical spatial resolution can be as low as 1 μm . Gardiner et al [11] have recently demonstrated the wide applicability of the Raman-microscope and are optimistic about the prospect of Raman mapping of surfaces using programmed stepper motor driven stages.

Rogers [12] has recently described the use of the Raman effect in optical fibre sensors, by the Distributed Anti-Stokes Raman Thermometry (DART) technique. The technique is the first to use a non-linear optical effect, it is independent on the fibre material and it measures absolute temperature and (in principle) requires no calibration. Resolution along the fibre was 5K in temperature and 5 m in fibre length.

The literature on infra-red and Raman spectroscopy is collected together on a database [13]. Between 1982 and September 1984 there were 7226 references from 106 journals. Raman spectroscopy is the major subject of a number of books [14-20] and a series of international conferences [21].

STUDY OF RESINS

Lu and Koenig [22] showed that the Raman spectra of Epon 825 epoxy resins are easily obtained and are sensitive to the degree of cure. The bisphenol A skeletal structure has strong lines at 640, 823, 1114, 1188, 1232 and 1608 cm^{-1} which are independent of the degree of cure. The epoxy group is characterised by strong lines at 768, 809, 862, and 1156 cm^{-1} which are sensitive to the degree of cure.

PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF FIBRES

Lespade et al [23] used Raman microprobe spectrometry to determine the degree of graphitisation of PAN-based carbon fibre on a micrometre scale. Similar studies of pyrocarbons and highly oriented or deposited chemicals were reported from the vapour phase, tar and anthracene cokes and non-graphitisable sucrose.

Sasaki and Nishina [24] studied the evolution of Raman spectra of carbon fibres made from pitch or polyacrylonitrile during several heat treatment processes, following the structural and compositional transformation from pitch to graphite. The scattering efficiency decreased gradually as the heat treatment temperature increased. Treatment at 1000°C reduced scattering by a factor of 1/8, while treatment at 2400°C reduced the efficiency to become comparable with highly oriented pyrolytic graphite (HOPG).

Katagiri et al [25] studied the Raman spectra of graphite and graphite fibres. Most previous measurements were taken from the basal planes but this study examined the edge planes which are important in such anisotropic and heterogeneous carbon materials. The work established an edge plane measurement condition and examined the radial distribution of fibre graphitisation.

Matsumura et al [26] used Raman scattering and x-ray diffraction to examine highly electroconductive graphite fibres prepared by the pyrolysis of cyanoacetylene onto carbon fibres with subsequent heat treatment. Many thin graphite strata were observed, cylindrically layered and scrolled around the core of the original fibre. The cyanoacetylene forms a more highly graphitised fibre than benzene.

Heremans et al [27] reported the thermal conductivity of graphite fibres, derived from polyacrylonitrile, pitch or CVD methane, in the temperature range 12–300 K. First-order Raman spectra were obtained by use of a microprobe. The lines at 1360 cm^{-1} (disorder induced) and at 1580 cm^{-1} (Raman allowed) were taken and the intensity ratio $I(1360)/I(1580)$ was found to correlate well with the amplitude of the low-temperature thermal-conductivity data. A defect-limited phonon mean free path length deduced from the Kelly model was found to correlate with the electrical resistivity and various characteristic molecular distances.

Intercalation, defined as the insertion of foreign atoms or molecules in a lattice, provides a unique method for the modification of the properties of carbon fibres. Dresselhaus [28] has reviewed the physical properties of intercalated carbon fibres and contrasted the behaviour of the fibres with bulk graphite. Raman spectroscopy, x-ray diffraction and electron microscopy are amongst the characterisation methods used.

Eventova et al [29] used Raman microanalysis to study the crystallinity, and chemical composition of microparticles and microinclusions,

in carbon fibres.

Atyaksheva et al [30] studied the chemisorption of ozone-oxygen mixtures on carbon fibre surfaces, using Raman spectroscopy, infra-red multiple-ATR spectroscopy and XPS. The oxidation process was accompanied by the formation of oxygen-containing functional groups on the fibre surfaces.

Wunder and Merajver [31] used Raman spectroscopy to study ultrahigh-molecular-weight-polyethylene (UHMWPE) in the temperature range 135-208°C, where optical anisotropy has been observed to exist. Spectroscopic evidence suggests that ordered domains persist at temperatures above the calorimetrically determined melting point. The domains disappear as the temperature is further increased but no calorimetric phase change is observed. The melt anisotropy is ascribed to oriented slowly melting superheated crystals.

STUDIES OF THE INTERFACE

Tuinistra and Koenig [32] used Raman spectroscopy to characterise the surfaces of carbon and graphite fibres. The Raman spectrum was correlated with the shear strength of the composite, reflecting the fibre surface treatment. Weak planes of graphite oriented parallel to the fibre surface were observed in many fibres.

Koenig and Shih [33] used a laser Raman technique to confirm the reversible nature of silanol hydrolysis at the coupling-agent to glass-fibre interface as a dynamic equilibrium between the coupling agent and penetrant water molecules. The reinforcing E-glass fibre treated with VTES (vinyl tri ethoxy silane) coupling agent was contained in a PMMA (polymethyl methacrylate) matrix. The intensity of the Si-O-Si symmetric stretching line (788 cm^{-1}) was reversible. After exposure to water or 100% RH, the line moved to a vinyl silane homopolymer position (783 cm^{-1}). Three days heat treatment (110°C) restored the line to 788 cm^{-1} . The coupling agent was shown to be both chemically bonded to the glass surface and copolymerised with the methylmethacrylate at the interface.

Shih [34] studied the chemical reaction between a methacryl silane coupling agent on glass fibre and the styrene monomer in unsaturated polyester resin using laser Raman spectroscopy. The styrene spectrum of the sample was identical to that of the homopolymer, but the carbonyl stretching frequency (1718 cm^{-1}) in the unreacted silane shifted (to 1702 cm^{-1}) after polymerisation. The results indicated that the styrene

was homopolymerised, with the silane grafted to the chain end. The silanes did not react with the polyester resin in the absence of the styrene monomer.

Koenig et al [35] used laser Raman spectroscopy to demonstrate the various structures which result from the molecular adsorption of silanol onto glass. A series of lines around $1050\text{--}950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were ascribed to the silanol Si-O stretching mode. Glass microspheres displayed lines at 980 cm^{-1} (wet samples) and 1005 cm^{-1} (dry samples). These lines relate to the hydrogen bonding between the silanol and the adsorbed water molecules. An additional line (992 cm^{-1}) was due to hydrogen bonding between adjacent silanols.

Ishida et al [36] adopted UV-RRS (ultraviolet resonance Raman spectroscopy) for the detection of molecular-thickness layers of a new potential coupling agent for fibreglass composites. Raman and FT-IR (Fourier-transform infra-red) spectroscopy both proved insufficiently sensitive. The UV-RRS technique shows a wider selection of excitation lines than the restricted visible spectrum. The coupling agent had a major resonance Raman enhancement at 363.8 nm , (50-fold in KBr and 200-fold in benzene), with a much greater apparent enhancement as a surface species. The technique is thus well-suited to the study of surfaces and especially monomolecular layers. The 1545 cm^{-1} line in the silane spectrum, which is sensitive to intermolecular interactions, is also subject to major enhancement.

MECHANICAL LOADING

Penn and Milanovich [37] found that no general change in the chemical structure of aramid fibres occurred on exposure to heat, radiation or stress during studies with Raman spectroscopy. The spectrum of a stressed filament was found to show increasing polarisation of all bands with increasing stress. The polymer responds to the load by a slight opening of the angle in the amide linkage of the chain and by improved alignment of the crystallites along the fibre axis. A table of the spectral peaks and assignments for Kevlar and its precursors is included in the reference.

Galiotis et al [38] used resonance Raman spectroscopy (RRS) to determine the frequencies of the vibrational modes in the backbone chain of polydiacetylene (PDA) fibres and the dependence of those frequencies on the tensile strain. The resonant enhancement can be obtained from fibres

covered by several millimetres of "reasonably transparent" resin matrix. Lap-joints between two PDA fibres cemented with epoxy resin were studied in tensile loading. The RRS utilised a 100 μm diameter focal spot 676 nm line krypton laser to study the 2085 cm^{-1} vibration associated with the triple bond. The Raman frequencies were constant, within the experimental accuracy, for different positions in the single fibre region and within the lap-joint. The frequency-displacement relationship was approximately linear and showed no hysteresis.

Galiotis et al [39] showed that the RRS frequency associated with triple-bond stretching changed by $-20 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ under tensile load. The strain was measured to an accuracy of $\pm 0.05\%$ with a point-to-point resolution of about 100 μm . The fibre was thus proposed as an internal molecular strain gauge monitored optically by the laser-Raman technique. The single crystal fibres offer considerable potential for use as the reinforcement in stiff, strong all-polymer fibre-reinforced composites.

A model composite system, consisting of one single-crystal PDA fibre in transparent epoxy resin, was studied during tensile longitudinal strain [40]. The strain at all points along the fibre was monitored by resonance Raman spectroscopy while the matrix strain was monitored by conventional techniques. Reuss-type behaviour (equal stress in both the fibre and the matrix) was demonstrated below 0.5% matrix strain. At higher strains Voigt-type behaviour (increase of matrix strain matched by an equal increase in fibre strain) occurred. In the high strain region, the simple Cox shear-lag model provides a qualitative description which explains most of the observed results.

Young et al [41] extended the use of the RRS technique to the measurement of the distribution of fibre strains in composites containing bundles of PDA fibres. The matrix was either epoxy resin or a fibreglass/epoxy composite. Epoxy resin composites with a high volume fraction of PDA-fibres were investigated in both tension and compression.

Galiotis et al [42] measured the Raman spectra for a single Kevlar 49 aramid fibre subjected to uniaxial stress, in an attempt to resolve the discrepancy between the work by Penn and Milanovich on aramid fibres and the Queen Mary College work on PDA fibres. During the application of tensile stress, the whole Raman spectrum of the Kevlar fibre between 1100 and 1700 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency with distinct broadening of the peaks.

Young et al [43] reported a value of $5 \text{ cm}^{-1}/\%$ for the Raman frequency shift of Kevlar fibres with strain. Point-to-point variation of strain along individual fibres in polymer matrix composites was determined to a high degree of precision using laser beams focussed down to less than $2 \mu\text{m}$. Measurements were made of the dependence of transfer length upon fibre diameter. Preliminary studies were made on the effect of surface pre-treatment upon stress transfer and of the interaction between cracks and reinforcing fibres.

Kim and Hsu [44] used Raman spectroscopic-mechanical analysis to study the stress distribution in polydiacetylene or aramid single fibres in epoxy resin or in soft elastomers. The frequency or equivalent strain of the fibre was zero or nearly zero at the fibre end, reaching a plateau near the central region. The load left by the fibre was strongly dependent on the macroscopic strain in the sample. When the fibre was embedded in the epoxy matrix there were additional changes in the band position as a function of temperature. The additional increase in the frequency was attributed to the thermal stress due to the different thermal expansion of the fibre and the matrix. The stress distribution was affected by the ratio of the elastic moduli of the fibre and the matrix.

Kwizera et al [45] studied the Raman spectra, Young's modulus and resistivity of pitch and PAN-based graphite fibres. X-ray diffraction and Raman scattering gave strong evidence for staging during intercalation with certain donors (K, Rb, Cs), but not with acceptor compounds (FeCl_3 and AlCl_3). Measurements of the Young's modulus of single filaments showed no significant change with intercalation.

SUMMARY

The potential of Raman spectroscopy as a non-destructive testing technique has been reviewed. The method has been applied to monitor resin cure, to monitor graphitisation of carbon fibres, to study the interface and to measure fibre strains in-situ.

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